

Step-by-step tasks performed by participants for each scenario

Scenario 1: Service with the Health Institution (HI)

The **Nurse** and the **Patient** participate in Scenario 1

STEP 1

[NURSE] Log in to the system.

email: nurse2@gmail.com

password: 123enferm

[PATIENT] Log in to the system.

email: patient2@gmail.com

password: 123pac

STEP 2

[NURSE] In “Register Report”, select the type of record “Observation” to be registered.

STEP 3

[NURSE] Request the patient's CPF number and verify the identification.

STEP 4

[NURSE] Record “Observation” providing information about the vital signs collected from the patient by entering “Vital Sign” and “Value” information from the test. Example:

Vital Sign	Value
Pressure	120x70mmHg
Temperature	38.9 C
FC	115 bpm
SatO2	94%

Source: <https://www.sanarmed.com/caso-clinico-de-covid-19>

STEP 5

[NURSE] Confirm “Register Observation” to register the information, wait for the registration to finish.

STEP 6

[PATIENT] Check the Note in the list of “Records” and read the record stored by the Nurse.

**Nurse, in Scenario 1 - Step 4, are the vital signs that you can enter on the platform. But, it's not limited to just those. You can increment or change them as you wish.*

Scenario 2: Assistance with a Health Professional (HP)

The **Doctor** and the **Patient** participate in Scenario 2

STEP 1 [DOCTOR] Log in to the system. email: medico2@gmail.com password: 123med
STEP 2 [DOCTOR] Present the identification CPF for the patient to authorize access to the “Observation” record registered by the Nurse.
STEP 3 [PATIENT] In the Records listing, grant access to records for the physician.
STEP 4 [DOCTOR] Check the “Observation” record that was shared by the patient in the list.
STEP 5 [DOCTOR] In “Register Report”, select the type of record “Anamnesis” to be registered.
STEP 6 [DOCTOR] Request the CPF number to identify the patient.
STEP 7 [DOCTOR] Record responses to all questions answered by the patient for the Anamnesis.
STEP 8 [DOCTOR] Confirm “Register Anamnesis” to record the information.

Instructions and suggestions for the Patient profile

In **Scenario 2 - Step 7**, the Doctor will ask questions for Anamnesis that the Patient profile will answer. Due to an important subject that has been much debated in recent months, the patient's clinical case will show symptoms of Covid-19. Listed below are the questions the Doctor will ask, and we suggest the **Current Illness History** answer for the patient to answer, but it is not limited to just those. You, the patient, can increase or change them as you wish. You can also answer as you prefer to the following questions, which do not have to be true.

History Present Illness (HDA)

What's the main complaint? A - Headache, shortness of breath, fever, sore throat.

The onset of symptoms and duration of complaint. A - Seven days ago

Pain location. A - Head and throat.

Past Pathological History

Are you undergoing medical treatment with any medication? Do you have any allergies?

Recent surgery? Cardiac changes (Cardiopathies)? Hypertension? Diabetes?

Scenario 3: Conducting laboratory tests at the Medical Laboratory (ML)

The **Biomedical/Pharmaceutical** and the Patient participate in Scenario 3

<p>STEP 1 [BIOMEDICAL] Log in to the system. email: lab2@gmail.com password: 123lab</p>												
<p>STEP 2 [BIOMEDICAL] In “Register Report”, select the type of record “Exam” to be registered.</p>												
<p>STEP 3 [BIOMEDICAL] Request CPF number for patient identification and verify identification.</p>												
<p>[BIOMEDICAL] Record “Exam” providing information about the tests performed in the laboratory by entering the test “Name” and “Value” information. Example:</p> <table><thead><tr><th>Value</th><th>Test</th></tr></thead><tbody><tr><td>Heb</td><td>12.1</td></tr><tr><td>Leukogram</td><td>12,300 without deviation</td></tr><tr><td>Platelets</td><td>156 thousand</td></tr><tr><td>pO2</td><td>82</td></tr><tr><td>HCO3</td><td>3</td></tr></tbody></table> <p>Source: https://www.sanarmed.com/caso-clinico-de-covid-19</p>	Value	Test	Heb	12.1	Leukogram	12,300 without deviation	Platelets	156 thousand	pO2	82	HCO3	3
Value	Test											
Heb	12.1											
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<p>STEP 5 [BIOMEDICAL] Confirm “Register Exam” to register the information.</p>												
<p>STEP 6 [PATIENT] Read the record stored by the LM</p>												

Biomedical or Pharmacist, in **Scenario 3 - Step 4, are the clinical analysis values that you will enter on the platform. But, it's not limited to just those. You can increment or change them as you wish.*

Scenario 4: Assistance with a Health Professional (HP)

The **Doctor** and the **Patient** participate in Scenario 4

STEP 1 [DOCTOR] Present the identification number for the patient to authorize access to the “Exam” registered by the Biomedical Doctor.
STEP 2 [PATIENT] In the Records list, grant access to the “Exam” record for the physician.
STEP 3 [DOCTOR] Check the “Exam” record that was shared by the patient in the list.
STEP 4 [DOCTOR] Select the type of record “Medication” to be registered.
STEP 5 [DOCTOR] Request the CPF number to identify the patient.
STEP 6 [DOCTOR] Record medication and diagnosis by providing necessary information.
STEP 7 [DOCTOR] Confirm “Register Medication” for information registration.
STEP 8 [PATIENT] Read the records made by the doctor.

**Doctor, in Scenario 4 - Step 6, you will be able to simulate the prescription of medicines that are usually treated for the symptoms of Covid-19.*